

Virtual Synchronous Generator Design to Improve Frequency Support of Converter-Interfaced Systems

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Abstract—This paper presents a control strategy based on the virtual synchronous generator (VSG) concept to improve the frequency support of converter-interfaced systems. The strategy has the flexibility to set virtual inertia, power-frequency droop, damping, and response speed. In previous VSG designs, the response speed depends on the virtual inertia; therefore, both specifications cannot be selected independently. In the present paper, this limitation is overcome by using a VSG structure able to set the response speed independently of the other design specifications, giving an additional degree of freedom to provide frequency support. In addition, the ability to select the speed at which the VSG draws power from the dc side allows for better use of the available dc power supply. The proposed VSG does not require phase-locked loop to achieve the damping effect; it has a simple implementation and a systematic design procedure. The control strategy is validated in a multimachine case study based on the Argentinian power system, including several VSGs. Aspects such as oscillation damping and improvements in the rate of change of frequency (RoCoF) and frequency nadir are discussed and compared with previous VSGs.

Index Terms—Active power control, converter-interfaced generation, frequency stability, inertia emulation, rate of change of frequency (RoCoF), virtual synchronous machine.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE reduction of inertia in grids with high penetration of non-conventional energy sources poses a challenge for system operators [1]. Low-inertia systems are prone to large frequency deviations and high rate of change of frequency (RoCoF) during a tie-line outage or an imbalance between generation and load [2]. The frequency events that occurred in Europe on January 8, 2021 and July 24, 2021 showed the need for further research and new solutions to improve frequency control. To cope with frequency stability degradation, operators are increasing the requirements on converter-interfaced systems [3].

Several control strategies have been proposed to improve the frequency support of power converters. Strategies that emulate the behavior of a synchronous generator have received

This work was supported in part by the Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET) and in part by the CERVERA research programme of CDTI, the Industrial and Technological Development Centre of Spain, under the research Project HySGrid+ (CER-20191019). Paper no. TEC-00126-2023 (*Corresponding author: Andres E. Leon*).

Supplementary material for this paper can be downloaded from <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org>. It includes a report with additional parameters and descriptions.

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considerable attention in recent years [4]–[6]. This concept was first introduced in [7] as virtual synchronous machine (VISMA) and in [8] as virtual synchronous generator (VSG). Later, similar strategies were developed under the names of power-synchronization control [9], synchronverter [10]–[12], and synchronous power controller [13]–[19]. Adaptive strategies are proposed in [20]–[28], where the damping effect is achieved by changing the VSG parameters online. Improvements in the VSG reference tracking are also analyzed in [29]–[32]. The present work focuses on increasing the design flexibility of the VSG control against grid frequency disturbances.

Most VSGs use the classical swing equation to represent the synchronous generator dynamics. The damping term in swing equation-based VSGs has been implemented using a phase-locked loop (PLL) [33]–[37], a washout filter [38]–[40], and a nonlinear function [41]. VSGs without swing equation, such as those based on lead-lag compensation and proportional-integral (PI) control, can also be found in the literature [13]–[17]. On the other hand, VSGs can be classified according to whether they have fixed [9]–[19] or time-varying [20]–[28] parameters and whether they require PLL (see [26]–[28] and [33]–[37]) or not (see [13]–[19] and [38]–[40]). All these VSGs have advantages and disadvantages in terms of complexity, robustness, and damping capacity [42]; these issues are discussed in the present paper.

A VSG control has three main components: the active power control loop, the reactive power control loop, and the virtual impedance (or virtual admittance). The first one is responsible for frequency support, and its key element is the transfer function between the active power variation and the converter frequency. The choice of this transfer function is essential to meet specifications such as virtual inertia, power-frequency droop, damping, and closed-loop response speed (response time). The analysis of the relationship between response speed and virtual inertia in VSGs shows that the response speed depends on the virtual inertia: the higher the virtual inertia, the slower the response speed; therefore, the two specifications cannot be selected independently. This limitation is overcome in this work by modifying the VSG structure.

In the present paper, a VSG design able to set the four specifications mentioned above is proposed. The design provides an additional degree of freedom to support the system frequency by independently setting virtual inertia, power-frequency droop, damping, and response speed. The proposed VSG does not require PLL, has a systematic and straightforward design, and uses simple transfer functions, avoiding the complexity of adaptive strategies and making it more attractive from an implementation point of view.

The paper is organized as follows. Different VSGs and constraints in their design are discussed in Section II. The proposed VSG structure and guidelines for parameter selection are described in Section III. The evaluation of VSG performance and robustness is performed in Sections IV and V using small-signal stability and frequency stability analyses. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

II. BACKGROUND

Transfer function (1) represents the classical swing equation of a synchronous generator and is the basis for the implementation of many VSG controls [42]

$$\Delta\omega = \frac{1}{2Hs + D_s} (p^{\text{ref}} - p). \quad (1)$$

In this equation, H is the virtual inertia, D_s is the steady-state power-frequency droop, and ω and p are the angular frequency and the active power of the converter.

Fig. 1 shows the model of the active power control loop when a VSG is connected to the grid (see [13]–[17] for details), where G_{vsg} is the VSG transfer function, Ω_B is the system nominal angular frequency, $K_s = 1/X_t$ is the synchronizing power coefficient (in per unit), $X_t = X_v + X_e$ is the total reactance, and X_v and X_e are the virtual and external reactances, respectively; the grid frequency ω_g acts as a disturbance in the control loop. To evaluate and compare the steady-state and transient response of different VSGs, the following closed-loop transfer functions (from the grid frequency and the time derivative of the grid frequency to the VSG power variation) are defined:

$$G_D(s) = \frac{p^{\text{ref}} - p}{\Delta\omega_g} \quad (2)$$

$$G_H(s) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{p^{\text{ref}} - p}{\Delta\dot{\omega}_g}, \quad (3)$$

where $G_H(s) = \frac{1}{2}G_D(s)/s$ is verified. Transfer functions G_D and G_H determine the power-frequency droop characteristics and the inertial response of a VSG, respectively. They will be discussed in more detail in the next section.

A VSG based on (1), as used in [19] and [43], has only two design parameters: parameter H , which defines the virtual inertia, and parameter D_s , which provides the damping. However, D_s is given by the steady-state operating point (typically in the range of $D_s^{-1} = 5\%$), whereas $D_s = 0$ must be selected in applications that cannot provide steady-state primary frequency regulation. Therefore, the VSG structure (1) does not have the degree of freedom to choose a desired damping effect (see [5] and [12]–[16]). To solve this problem, VSGs with an additional damping term including a PLL are considered in [33]–[37].

A. VSG with PLL

A VSG with a damping term using the grid frequency obtained by a PLL is shown in Fig. 2 (hereinafter referred to as conventional VSG; C-VSG). Its dynamics is given by

$$\Delta\omega = G_{vsg}(s) (p^{\text{ref}} - p + D_t \Delta\dot{\omega}_g), \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1. Model of active power control loop using a generic VSG without PLL.

Fig. 2. Block diagram of a VSG with PLL [33]–[37].

Fig. 3. Model of active power control loop using C-VSG.

where $G_{vsg}(s) = \frac{1}{2Hs + D_s + D_t}$; D_t is the damping coefficient and $\tilde{\omega}_g$ is the frequency estimated by the PLL. In the C-VSG case, the active power control loop can be represented as shown in Fig. 3, and transfer function (2) results in

$$G_D(s) = \frac{(1 - P(s)D_t G_{vsg}(s)) G_g(s)}{1 + G_{vsg}(s) G_g(s)}, \quad (5)$$

where $G_g(s) = K_g/s$ and $K_g = \Omega_B K_s$. Because the PLL bandwidth is faster than the main VSG mode, $P(s) \approx 1$ can be considered at the design stage [27]; then (5) yields

$$G_D(s) = \frac{K_g (s + \frac{D_s}{2H})}{s^2 + \frac{D_s + D_t}{2H} s + \frac{K_g}{2H}}. \quad (6)$$

Applying the final value theorem [44], the steady-state value of transfer function (6) for a unit-step input can be obtained as

$$G_D^{ss} = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} s \frac{G_D(s)}{s} = D_s. \quad (7)$$

As expected, the result of (7) is the steady-state droop. The superscript ‘ss’ denotes steady-state value. Similarly, the steady-state value of G_H can be calculated as follows

$$G_H^{ss} = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} s \frac{G_H(s)}{s} = H. \quad (8)$$

Fig. 4. Block diagram of a VSG based on lead-lag compensation [13]–[15].

This result indicates that when the grid frequency drops at a constant rate $\dot{\omega}_g$, the converter delivers a power equivalent to a generator with an inertia constant H . In the calculation of (8), D_s is set to zero to isolate the inertial response from the primary frequency response.

Parameter D_t and closed-loop natural frequency ω_n can be obtained by equating the coefficients of the denominator polynomial of (6) with the coefficients of a desired closed-loop characteristic polynomial $p(s) = s^2 + 2\zeta\omega_n s + \omega_n^2$, resulting in

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{\frac{K_g}{2H}} \quad (9)$$

$$D_t = 4H\zeta\omega_n - D_s, \quad (10)$$

where ζ is the damping ratio of the closed-loop poles. Using (9) and (10), (6) can be rewritten as

$$G_D(s) = \frac{K_g s + D_s \omega_n^2}{s^2 + 2\zeta\omega_n s + \omega_n^2}. \quad (11)$$

The value of ω_n is related to the closed-loop bandwidth; it indicates the VSG response speed and how quickly the VSG draws power from the dc source.

Note that the C-VSG design has the constraint that, once the inertia H is chosen, the value of ω_n is determined by (9). In Section III, it is shown that setting H and ω_n independently provides an additional degree of freedom to shape the transient response of the VSG.

B. VSG without PLL

To avoid PLL, VSGs that do not require estimating the grid frequency are proposed in [13]–[19] and [38]–[40]. They have the general form

$$\Delta\omega = G_{vsg}(s) (p^{\text{ref}} - p). \quad (12)$$

In these VSGs, the model of the active power control loop is the one shown in Fig. 1, and transfer function (2) results in

$$G_D(s) = \frac{G_g(s)}{1 + G_{vsg}(s)G_g(s)}. \quad (13)$$

Two approaches that do not use PLL, such as the VSG with lead-lag compensation and the VSG with washout filter, are described below.

1) *VSG with Lead-Lag Compensation*: A VSG based on lead-lag compensation is proposed in [13]–[15] (see Fig. 4). Its VSG transfer function is given by

$$G_{vsg}(s) = \frac{K_p s + K_i}{s + K_G}. \quad (14)$$

Fig. 5. Block diagram of a VSG with washout filter [38]–[40].

Substituting (14) into (13) yields

$$G_D(s) = \frac{K_g (s + K_G)}{s^2 + (K_g K_p + K_G) s + K_g K_i}. \quad (15)$$

As in the previous section, the steady-state values of G_D and G_H are calculated using the final value theorem, obtaining $G_D^{ss} = K_G/K_i$ and $G_H^{ss} = 1/(2K_i)$. Then, parameters K_i and K_G are chosen to meet the desired specifications $G_D^{ss} = D_s$ and $G_H^{ss} = H$, resulting in $K_i = 1/(2H)$ and $K_G = D_s/(2H)$ (see [14]). Parameters K_p and ω_n are obtained by equating the denominator of (15) with the desired closed-loop characteristic polynomial $p(s) = s^2 + 2\zeta\omega_n s + \omega_n^2$

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{\frac{K_g}{2H}} \quad (16)$$

$$K_p = \frac{2\zeta\omega_n}{K_g} - \frac{D_s\omega_n^2}{K_g^2}. \quad (17)$$

The value of ω_n is equal to the one obtained in (9) for the C-VSG case, which is determined by the chosen virtual inertia; therefore, both approaches have the same constraint of not being able to set ω_n and H independently. Furthermore, substituting the values of K_p , K_i , and K_G into (15) results in the same closed-loop transfer function as that obtained in (11) for the C-VSG case.

Note that if steady-state power-frequency droop is not considered (i.e., $D_s = 0$), parameter K_G is zero and transfer function (14) becomes a PI control, which is the VSG structure used in [14]–[17]. This VSG is a special case of the VSG with lead-lag compensation, having the same constraint.

2) *VSG with Washout Filter*: A VSG with a damping term with washout filter is considered in [38]–[40] (see Fig. 5). In this case, the VSG transfer function results in

$$G_{vsg}(s) = \frac{T_w s + 1}{2HT_w s^2 + K_w s + D_s}, \quad (18)$$

where $K_w = 2H + (D_s + D_w)T_w$; parameters T_w and D_w are the time constant and the damping coefficient of the washout filter. Similar structures with two poles and one zero are designed using Bode plots and pole placement in [29] and [30], respectively. Substituting (18) into (13) yields

$$G_D(s) = \frac{K_g (2HT_w s^2 + K_w s + D_s)}{2HT_w s^3 + K_w s^2 + (K_g T_w + D_s) s + K_g}, \quad (19)$$

resulting in the values $G_D^{ss} = D_s$ and $G_H^{ss} = H + D_w T_w / 2$.

In summary, the drawback of the previous VSGs is that they cannot set the closed-loop response speed without modifying the virtual inertia [e.g., to increase ω_n , the inertia must be

Fig. 6. Block diagram of the proposed E-VSG.

TABLE I
SYSTEM PARAMETERS AND DESIGN SPECIFICATIONS

Description	Parameter	Value
system nominal angular frequency	Ω_B	314 rad/s
external reactance	X_e	0.1 pu
virtual reactance	X_v	0.2 pu
grid parameter	K_g	1047.2
virtual inertia	H	5 s
damping ratio	ζ	0.707
steady-state power-frequency droop	D_s	0
real pole location	α	10
nominal response speed	ω_n^0	10.23 rad/s

TABLE II
E-VSG PARAMETERS FOR DIFFERENT RESPONSE SPEEDS

ω_n	K	F	T
ω_n^0	0.1382	0.0019	0.1520
$1.33\omega_n^0$	0.0583	-0.0031	0.1140
$1.67\omega_n^0$	0.0299	-0.0054	0.0912
$2\omega_n^0$	0.0173	-0.0067	0.0760

decreased; see (9)]. In the following section, a VSG structure is proposed to overcome this limitation and to be able to independently set the four specifications: inertia H , power-frequency droop D_s , damping ζ , and response speed ω_n .

III. PROPOSED VSG STRUCTURE

In this section, a VSG with enhanced design flexibility is introduced. This VSG has two poles and two zeros with the following structure (hereinafter referred to as enhanced VSG; E-VSG)

$$G_{vs_g}(s) = \frac{Fs^2 + Ts + 1}{Ks^2 + 2Hs + D_s}. \quad (20)$$

The block diagram of the E-VSG is shown in Fig. 6, and the state-space representation is given by

$$\dot{x}_v = p^{\text{ref}} - p - D_s \Delta\omega \quad (21)$$

$$\dot{x}_w = x_v + T(p^{\text{ref}} - p) - 2H\Delta\omega, \quad (22)$$

where $\Delta\omega = (x_w + F(p^{\text{ref}} - p)) / K$. In this case, transfer function (13) results in

$$G_D(s) = \frac{\frac{K_g}{K}(Ks^2 + 2Hs + D_s)}{s^3 + \frac{2H + K_g F}{K}s^2 + \frac{K_g T + D_s}{K}s + \frac{K_g}{K}}, \quad (23)$$

which meets the specifications $G_D^{ss} = D_s$ and $G_H^{ss} = H$.

Parameters K , F , and T are chosen to obtain a desired location of the closed-loop poles. To this end, the following closed-loop characteristic polynomial is selected

$$p(s) = (s^2 + 2\zeta\omega_n s + \omega_n^2)(s + \alpha\zeta\omega_n). \quad (24)$$

This polynomial consists of a pair of complex poles $\lambda_{1,2} = -\zeta\omega_n \pm j\omega_n\sqrt{1 - \zeta^2}$ and a real pole $\lambda_3 = -\alpha\zeta\omega_n$. By equating the coefficients of the denominator of (23) with the coefficients of polynomial (24) and solving the resulting equation system, the E-VSG parameters are given by

$$K = \frac{K_g}{\alpha\zeta\omega_n^3} \quad (25)$$

$$F = \frac{\alpha + 2}{\alpha\omega_n^2} - \frac{2H}{K_g} \quad (26)$$

$$T = \frac{2\alpha\zeta^2 + 1}{\alpha\zeta\omega_n} - \frac{D_s}{K_g}. \quad (27)$$

In the E-VSG design, the response speed ω_n can be chosen independently of the virtual inertia H . Substituting (25)-(27) into (23) yields

$$G_D(s) = \frac{K_g s^2 + \alpha\zeta\omega_n^3(2Hs + D_s)}{(s^2 + 2\zeta\omega_n s + \omega_n^2)(s + \alpha\zeta\omega_n)}. \quad (28)$$

Parameter α is chosen so that real pole λ_3 is a decade higher than complex poles $\lambda_{1,2}$ (i.e., setting $\alpha = 10$); in this way, dynamics (28) behaves as a second-order system. In the following, for a fair comparison, the damping ratio is set to $\zeta = 0.707$ in all considered VSG designs.

By using $\omega_n = \omega_n^0 = \sqrt{K_g/(2H)}$, and after some mathematical manipulations, a (stable) pole-zero cancellation occurs at $s = -\alpha\zeta\omega_n$, and closed-loop transfer function (28) results in (11). Therefore, VSGs with closed-loop transfer function (11) are a special case of E-VSG with $\omega_n = \omega_n^0$, and have the same transient response. However, as will be shown below, the E-VSG design has the additional degree of freedom to select different values for ω_n and modify the transient response.

The E-VSG design procedure can be summarized as follows: select the desired virtual inertia H and steady-state droop D_s ; then, select the value of ω_n (e.g., $\omega_n = 1.5\omega_n^0$ can be chosen to obtain a response 50% faster than C-VSG); finally, calculate parameters K , F , and T using expressions (25)-(27).

An introductory example is considered to evaluate the VSG inertial response and to show the design flexibility of the E-VSG. The system parameters and design specifications are shown in Table I. In this case, the C-VSG damping coefficient results in $D_t = 144.7$, and the E-VSG parameters for different values of ω_n are shown in Table II. The test consists of connecting a VSG to an ac voltage source (emulating the grid voltage) and, at 0.1 s, reducing the voltage source frequency at a rate of 1 Hz/s for 1 s (see Fig. 7).

The equation of motion of a rotating mass with inertia H can be expressed in terms of power and in per-unit values as follows [45]

$$2H\dot{\omega}_g = \Delta p. \quad (29)$$

The power that a VSG with inertia H should deliver to the grid when the grid frequency drops at a rate of $\dot{\omega}_g$ can

Fig. 7. Transient response of different VSGs to a grid frequency ramp. Top subplot: variation of the converter output power. Bottom subplot: virtual rotor speed (colored line) and grid frequency (gray line).

be calculated from (29). In this example, this power results in $\Delta p = 2H\dot{\omega}_g = 2 \times 5 \times \frac{2\pi}{\Omega_B} = 0.2$ pu. Fig. 7(a) shows the responses of C-VSG, VSG with lead-lag compensation (L-VSG), VSG with washout filter (W-VSG), and E-VSG with $\omega_n = \omega_n^0$. All VSGs deliver a power equal to $\Delta p = 0.2$ pu, corresponding to an inertia constant $H = 5$ s, as calculated from (29). In Fig. 7(a), VSGs have a similar transient response because they have been designed with the same specifications (inertia, damping, etc., see Table I); only small differences are observed due to the PLL dynamics of the C-VSG and the additional pole of the VSG with washout filter. To meet these specifications, all VSG parameters were used; for example, in the C-VSG case, once the inertia H is chosen, the value of the response speed ω_n is fixed and determined by (9); in this case, the response speed can be increased, but at the expense of reducing the virtual inertia. On the other hand, the E-VSG has an additional parameter that can be used to achieve the same specifications with a different value of ω_n . This provides an additional degree of freedom to determine the location of a zero in closed-loop transfer function (28) and modify the transient response of the VSG. To illustrate this point, the effect of increasing the value of ω_n in the E-VSG response is shown in Fig. 7(b). In order to allow a faster power injection into the grid, the VSG control increases the angle difference between the converter voltage and the grid voltage by rapidly changing its internal variables (see the increase in the virtual rotor speed when the grid frequency starts to drop).

IV. CASE STUDY

A. Description

The VSG is validated in a multimachine power system based on the Argentinian network (see Fig. 8). The system consists of 89 buses, 22 conventional power plants, 2 solar power plants, and 11 wind farms. Synchronous generators are represented by a sixth-order model and are equipped with automatic voltage regulator, power system stabilizer, and

turbine-governor system [46]. Solar power plants are a small part of the generation mix and are considered as constant power sources. Wind farms are modeled using full-converter (Type 4) wind turbine generators [47]. To improve the system frequency response, VSG control is applied to converter-interfaced systems. As an example, converters of Type 4 wind turbines are used in this work. The VSG control and maximum power point tracking (MPPT) are implemented in the grid-side converter (GSC), and the dc-bus voltage regulation is achieved by the machine-side converter (MSC); see control philosophy in [48]. Fig. 9 shows an overview of the control system. Cases in which GSCs use C-VSG, the proposed E-VSG, and a vector control (i.e., no frequency support, called BASE case) are analyzed. Two E-VSGs are defined: $\omega_n = 1.5\omega_n^0$ (50% faster than C-VSG, called E-VSG^{fast}) and $\omega_n = 0.5\omega_n^0$ (50% slower than C-VSG, called E-VSG^{slow}).

The external reactance X_e (used to calculate parameter K_g) is required in the VSG design. In a multimachine power system, the value of this reactance can be obtained in per-unit values as the inverse of the short-circuit power or calculated from the system admittance matrix using the procedure described in [49]. Due to space limitations, this procedure and the E-VSG parameters are uploaded to IEEE DataPort [50]. Other parameters are set to $K_q^{-1} = 5\%$, $T_q = 0.03$ s, $R_v = 0$, and $L_v = 0.2$ pu. In the wind turbine, the power-speed characteristic is taken from [51], the dc bus has a nominal voltage $v_{dc} = 1.3$ kV with a capacitive energy of 15 kJ/MVA, the generator and turbine have a total inertia $H_w = 4$ s, and the inductances are $L_g = 0.15$ pu and $L_s = 0.1$ pu.

Time-domain simulations are performed following the procedure described in [45] for transient stability analysis of multimachine power systems. The system model consists of a set of nonlinear differential-algebraic equations (DAE). The dynamics of machine rotor circuits, excitation and turbine-governor systems, and other devices are represented by differential equations, whereas fast transients associated with

Fig. 8. Single-line diagram of the Argentinian power system.

the transmission network are neglected and the network is represented by algebraic equations. Balanced three-phase conditions are assumed, and power converters are represented by an average model. The implicit trapezoidal method is used to solve the DAE system (see details in [46]). Variables in the network and converter synchronous reference frames are denoted by the subscripts D - Q and d - q , respectively.

B. Small-Signal Stability Analysis

Fig. 10(a) shows the system eigenvalues for the BASE case and for the C-VSG and E-VSG^{fast} cases with virtual inertia $H = 5$ s. The eigenvalues (modes) associated with the C-VSG and the E-VSG^{fast} are indicated by red and blue areas, respectively. These eigenvalues are identified using participation factor analysis [45]. The damping ratio of the C-VSG modes is significantly lower than the design value of $\zeta = 0.707$. As in Fig. 10(a), Fig. 10(b) shows the system eigenvalues, but considering the C-VSG and E-VSG^{slow} cases with virtual inertia $H = 25$ s. In this test, the C-VSG modes

have a damping ratio between 0.1 and 0.4, whereas the E-VSG modes are close to the desired value of $\zeta = 0.707$. Although both VSGs are designed to have the same damping, when implemented in a practical power system (i.e., when the infinite bus assumption does not hold), E-VSG is more robust and meets the design specifications more accurately than C-VSG.

C. Performance Evaluation

Fig. 11 shows the system response to a 200 MW load increase at the bus near generator 209 (located in a relatively weak area of the system; see Fig. 8). In the tests, the disturbance is applied at $t = 1$ s. The BASE, C-VSG, and E-VSG cases are represented by yellow, red, and blue lines, respectively. In this first test, E-VSG is designed with $\omega_n = 1.5\omega_n^0$ (E-VSG^{fast}) and $H = 5$ s. The frequency of synchronous generators is shown in Fig. 11(a); the RoCoF of generators 209 and 2625 is shown in Fig. 11(b) and (c), respectively. RoCoF is calculated over an averaging window of 20 ms (one cycle). The faster power delivery of E-VSG^{fast} allows a higher reduction in the RoCoF at the moment of the disturbance; for example, a RoCoF improvement of 15.8% is observed in Fig. 11(b) when comparing the E-VSG and C-VSG cases. Fig. 12 presents the RoCoF of all synchronous generators at the moment of the disturbance, showing a reduction in RoCoF when using E-VSG. The faster control action of the E-VSG^{fast} results in a higher VSG output power and also in a higher dc-bus voltage variation; however, these variations are within a normal range [see Figs. 11(d) and (e)]. This test is repeated, but considering the outage of generator 2629 as disturbance. As in the previous test, E-VSG^{fast} achieves a lower RoCoF in all synchronous generators (see Fig. 13).

Next, the load increase test is analyzed, but this time E-VSG is designed with $\omega_n = 0.5\omega_n^0$ (E-VSG^{slow}; see Fig. 14). This design allows slowing down the power delivered by the VSG, which increases the support at the frequency nadir moment. Improving the system frequency nadir requires more energy, so both E-VSG^{slow} and C-VSG are designed with $H = 25$ s. The frequency of synchronous generators and the frequency of the center of inertia (CoI) are shown in Figs. 14(a) and (b), respectively. The CoI frequency nadir of the BASE case is improved by 6.5% with C-VSG and by 12.1% with E-VSG^{slow} [see Fig. 14(b)]; both have a similar performance in terms of RoCoF reduction just after the disturbance [see Fig. 14(c)]. In agreement with the small-signal analysis shown in Fig. 10(b), E-VSG has a more damped response than C-VSG in a practical multimachine system [see VSG output power in Fig. 14(d)]. The test in Fig. 14 is repeated considering the outage of generator 2629, obtaining similar conclusions (see Fig. 15).

The performance of the E-VSG is compared to VSGs without PLL described in Section II-B. Results show that a reduction in RoCoF is also achieved when using E-VSG (see results in IEEE DataPort [50]).

V. ROBUSTNESS EVALUATION

This section analyzes the performance of the E-VSG with respect to system variations. First, the introductory example

Fig. 9. Block diagram of the proposed control strategy and schematic of the wind turbine generator system.

Fig. 10. Eigenvalues of the system corresponding to different control strategies. (a) BASE, C-VSG, and E-VSG^{fast} cases with $H = 5$ s are shown with yellow circles, red circles, and blue crosses, respectively. (b) BASE, C-VSG, and E-VSG^{slow} cases with $H = 25$ s are shown with yellow circles, red circles, and blue crosses, respectively.

described in Section III is analyzed. Fig. 16(a) shows the eigenvalue trajectory when external reactance X_e varies from 0.01 pu to 0.5 pu; VSG parameters are designed for nominal value $X_e^0 = 0.1$ pu. It is observed that the higher the value of ω_n , the higher the sensitivity to reactance variations. An eigenvalue reduces its damping as X_e increases, but the system is stable with a damping ratio higher than $\zeta = 0.36$ even for $X_e = 0.5$ pu [i.e., short-circuit ratio (SCR) = 2]. In Fig. 16(a), the scenarios with $X_e = X_e^0$ and $X_e = 2X_e^0$ are indicated by blue and green circles, respectively. This second scenario occurs when the VSG is connected to the system through two transmission lines and one of them is out of service; in this case, a damping ratio higher than $\zeta = 0.54$ is achieved.

The test described in Fig. 7 is used to illustrate the transient response of the VSG. The VSG output power when the system operates at point A and point B [see Fig. 16(a)] is shown

in Fig. 16(b) with blue and green lines, respectively. For comparison, the cases in which the VSG is designed for the actual external reactance are shown with the solid yellow line. As expected, for point A (i.e., nominal case), the blue line and the corresponding yellow line coincide, whereas for point B, the green line has a larger overshoot (lower damping); however, the overshoot is less than 15% and the desired final value is reached with no steady-state error.

The robustness of the E-VSG is also analyzed using the multimachine case study. For this purpose, an eigenvalue analysis is performed to evaluate the sensitivity of E-VSG modes to changes in the network topology (see Fig. 17). Single-line ($N-1$) contingencies are considered to generate different network topologies (see Fig. 8). E-VSGs are designed with $\omega_n = 1.5\omega_n^0$ and for the normal condition. E-VSG modes for contingency conditions (colored circles in the blue area)

Fig. 11. System response to a 200 MW load increase. Comparison of BASE case, C-VSG, and E-VSG designed with $\omega_n = 1.5\omega_n^0$ (E-VSG^{fast}). (a) Frequency of synchronous generators. (b) RoCoF of generator 209, time window after the disturbance. (c) RoCoF of generator 2625. (d) VSG output power variation. (e) DC-bus voltages.

shift to the right (lower damping ratio) compared to E-VSG modes for normal conditions (blue crosses); however, the shift of E-VSG modes is not significant and their damping ratio is higher than $\zeta = 0.51$.

VI. CONCLUSION

A VSG design was presented to improve the frequency support of converter-interfaced systems. The proposed VSG is able to independently set specifications such as virtual inertia, power-frequency droop, damping, and response speed. The VSG has a systematic design procedure and a simple implementation that does not require PLL; its effectiveness

Fig. 12. RoCoF comparison of the BASE, C-VSG, and E-VSG cases for the load increase test.

Fig. 13. RoCoF comparison of the BASE, C-VSG, and E-VSG cases for the generator outage test.

was validated in a multimachine power system through eigenvalue and transient response analyses. High damping capacity and flexibility to support RoCoF and frequency nadir were obtained. In order to achieve an adequate performance, the parameters of each VSG were designed considering the short-circuit power of the bus to which the converter is connected. Improvements in power converter control will allow higher penetration of renewable energy sources without compromising the frequency stability.

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Fig. 14. System response to a 200 MW load increase. Comparison of BASE case, C-VSG, and E-VSG designed with $\omega_n = 0.5\omega_n^0$ (E-VSG^{slow}). (a) Frequency of synchronous generators. (b) Frequency of the center of inertia. (c) RoCoF of generator 209. (d) VSG output power variation. (e) DC-bus voltages.

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